

An Investigation on Intellectual Intuition Domains Influencing Instructional Approach of Teachers in Technology-Mediated Classroom: A Mixed Method Research

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Abstract. This study explored the significant relationship between intellectual intuition and instructional approach of teachers in technology-mediated classroom. In this study, the researcher selected the 155 public elementary school teachers in Buhangin District in Davao City as the study's respondents in the quantitative phase. In comparison, 10 teachers were chosen for IDI and FGD in the qualitative phase. Mixed method research design using explanatory sequential approach was employed. The data collected were subjected to the following statistical tools: Mean and Pearson-r Correlation Analysis. Findings revealed that teachers' intellectual intuition was rated as extensive, while the instructional approach of teachers in technology-mediated classrooms was rated as moderately extensive. Correlation analysis proved a significant relationship between intellectual intuition and instructional approach of teachers in technology-mediated classroom in Buhangin District in Davao City. Thematic analysis confirmed the extensive rating on intellectual intuition, and the moderately extensive rating on instructional approach of teachers in technology-mediated classroom. Thematic analysis showed that the codes, critical thinking, multimodal learning, and efficiency, confirmed the significant relationship between intellectual intuition and instructional approach of teachers in technology-mediated classroom.

KEY WORDS

1. explanatory sequential approach 2. intellectual intuition 3. instructional approach in technology-mediated classroom

Date Received: January 05, 2025 — Date Reviewed: February 15, 2025 — Date Published: March 15, 2025

1. Introduction

Intellectual intuition played a critical role in shaping the instructional approach of teachers in technology-mediated classrooms by enabling them to make swift, effective decisions regarding integrating digital tools and resources. Teachers with strong intellectual intuition intuitively assessed the needs of their students and adapted their teaching strategies to incorporate technology in ways that enhanced engagement and learning outcomes. The importance of mixed method analysis in this context lay in its ability to comprehensively understand how intellectual intuition influenced instructional practices. By combining quantitative data, such as student performance metrics, with qualitative insights from teacher interviews and classroom observations, mixed method analysis offered a holistic view of the effectiveness of technology

integration. This approach allowed researchers to capture the complexity of teaching and learning processes, uncovering how intellectual intuition impacted educational outcomes and informing best practices for technology-mediated instruction. Technology integration in classrooms has been a significant focus, yet many teachers face issues and challenges that result in poor instructional approaches. In the USA, one of the main challenges is the digital divide, where disparities in access to technology and internet connectivity hinder effective technology-mediated instruction (Van Dijk, 2020). Teachers in under-resourced schools struggle with outdated equipment and insufficient training, leading to suboptimal use of digital tools. Additionally, the lack of ongoing professional development opportunities leaves many educators ill-equipped to incorporate new technologies effectively into their teaching practices (Trust, 2018). This results in a reliance on traditional methods that fail to leverage the potential benefits of technology, ultimately impacting student engagement and learning outcomes. In Asia similar challenges are evident, but additional cultural and systemic factors compound them. For instance, in many Asian countries, the education system is heavily exam-oriented, which can limit the willingness of teachers to experiment with technology in ways that may not directly contribute to exam performance (Cheng Lam, 2019). Furthermore, a lack of localized digital content often aligns with the curriculum, making it difficult for teachers to find appropriate resources (Sirikul Donmuang, 2021). Another significant issue is the varying levels of technological infrastructure across different regions, particularly in rural areas, which hampers consistent technology integration (Hashim Tan, 2020). This results in a digital divide between countries and within them, exacerbating educational inequalities and affecting the overall effectiveness of technology-mediated instruction. The shift to technology-mediated classrooms in the Philippines, accelerated by the COVID-19 pandemic, has revealed significant challenges. Many teachers face poor digital literacy, which hampers their ability to integrate technology into their teaching practices effectively. This issue is compounded by inadequate training and professional development opportunities, leaving teachers ill-equipped to navigate new educational technologies. Additionally, the digital divide remains a significant barrier, with disparities in access to reliable internet and digital resources, particularly in rural areas, exacerbating the difficulties in implementing effective technology-mediated instruction (Bustillo Aguilos, 2022). Similar challenges are observed in Davao City, but with some localized nuances. Teachers often struggle with limited access to modern educational technologies due to budget constraints and the lack of robust infrastructure. While striving to integrate technology, the city's educational system faces hurdles such as inconsistent power supply and internet connectivity, which disrupt the learning process. Additionally, the diverse socioeconomic backgrounds of students mean that not all have access to personal digital devices, creating an uneven playing field in technology-mediated learning environments (Ermita et al., 2021). Most previous studies on the influence of intellectual intuition on teachers' instructional approaches in technology-mediated classrooms have been predominantly qualitative or quantitative. These studies often focused on isolated aspects of teaching strategies or teacher perceptions without integrating both qualitative and quantitative insights. Furthermore, to the researcher's knowledge, no comprehensive study has been conducted specifically within the Philippine setting. This gap highlights the need for a mixed-method analysis that combines the depth of qualitative data with the breadth of quantitative data to provide a more holistic understanding of the phenomenon. The relevance of conducting this study in the Philippine con-

text is underscored by the unique challenges and opportunities presented by the country's educational landscape. Filipino teachers face distinct issues such as varying levels of access to technology, differences in digital literacy, and diverse student populations. This study aims to uncover nuanced insights into how intellectual intuition influences instructional practices

in technology-mediated classrooms by employing a mixed-method approach. Such an approach fills the existing research gap. It provides valuable data that can inform policy decisions, teacher training programs, and the development of more effective teaching strategies tailored to the Philippine context.

2. Methodology

This section contains the research design, research respondents, research instrument, data gathering procedure, and data analysis.

2.1. Research Design—The researcher employed mixed methods in this study, specifically an explanatory sequential research design. Toyon (2021) defined a mixed method research design as a research approach that combined elements of both qualitative and quantitative methodologies. It involved collecting and analyzing both quantitative data (such as numerical measurements or statistical analyses) and qualitative data (such as observations or interviews) to gain a more comprehensive understanding of the research topic. Mixed method research designs were employed when researchers sought to explore complex phenomena that could not be fully understood using only one methodological approach. By combining quantitative and qualitative data collection and analysis techniques, researchers could complement each other's strengths and weaknesses, providing a more nuanced and holistic understanding of the research problem. An explanatory sequential approach was a mixed methods approach where quantitative data was collected and analyzed first, followed by qualitative data collection and analysis to provide additional depth and understanding (Birgili Demir, 2022). In this design, the quantitative phase typically preceded the qualitative phase, and the qualitative phase was used to help explain or elaborate on the quantitative findings. This sequen-

tial process allowed researchers to gain a more comprehensive understanding of the research problem by integrating both quantitative and qualitative perspectives. By combining quantitative and qualitative data in a sequential manner, researchers could gain deeper insights and provide a more comprehensive analysis of the research topic (Othman, Steen Fleet, 2020). In the quantitative phase, the researcher specifically used correlational research techniques to gather data, ideas, facts, and information related to the study. The descriptive-correlational approach was a type of research method that aimed to establish the relationship or association between two or more variables without implying causation. In this design, researchers measured the degree of relationship or correlation between variables to understand how changes in one variable may be related to changes in another. Correlational research typically involved collecting data on the variables of interest from a sample population and then analyzing the data to determine if there was a relationship between them (Pace, 2019). In the context of this study, correlational research design allowed the researcher to examine the relationship between the intellectual intuition domains and instructional approach in technology-mediated classroom. In the qualitative phase, the researcher used a phenomenological approach. A phe-

phenomenological study was a methodology used to explore and understand individuals' lived experiences, perceptions, and perspectives of a particular phenomenon. It focused on uncovering the essence or meaning of these experiences from the participants' perspectives (Williams, 2021). Phenomenological inquiry was highly appropriate for explaining the influence of intellectual intuition domains on instructional approaches in technology-mediated classrooms as it delved into teachers' lived experiences, capturing the essence of their intuitive decision-making processes. This qualitative method allowed researchers to explore teachers' subjective experiences and perceptions, providing rich, detailed insights into how intellectual intuition shaped their instructional strategies and interactions with technology. By focusing on the teachers' firsthand accounts, phenomenological inquiry could uncover the deeper meanings and contextual factors that quantitative methods might have overlooked, thereby offering a holistic understanding of the phenomenon (Creswell, 2016). A sequential explanatory mixed method design was highly appropriate for studying the influence of intellectual intuition domains on the instructional approach in technology-mediated classrooms of teachers. This design allowed researchers first to gather and analyze quantitative data to identify patterns and relationships, providing a broad overview of how intellectual intuition impacted instructional strategies. Following this, qualitative data collection offered in-depth insights into these patterns, helping to explain the underlying reasons and contextual factors behind the quantitative results, thereby creating a comprehensive understanding of the phenomenon (Creswell Plano Clark, 2018).

2.2. Research Respondents—Quantitative Phase. The study's respondents were the teachers in Buhangin District, Davao City. In this study, 155 respondents were selected through a stratified random sampling technique. Stratified random sampling is a method of sampling

that involves the division of a population into smaller sub-groups known as strata. According to Shi (2015), in stratified random sampling, or stratification, the strata are formed based on members' shared attributes or characteristics such as income or educational attainment. Stratified random sampling is appropriate in this study because there is heterogeneity in a population that can be classified with ancillary information. The primary consideration of this study is to select respondents who can provide information to achieve the purpose of this study. The inclusion criteria are as follows: participants must be currently employed as elementary school teachers in Buhangin District, Davao City to ensure relevance to the study's focus on instructional approaches in elementary education; participants should have at least one year of experience using technology in their classrooms to ensure they have sufficient exposure to technology-mediated teaching; and participants must be willing to engage in both quantitative and qualitative phases of the study, including surveys, interviews, and possible classroom observations. Qualitative Phase. Qualitative Phase. The researcher purposively selected 5 elementary school teachers for the in-depth interview (IDI) and five elementary school teachers for the focus group discussion (FGD). A total of 10 elementary school teachers in Buhangin District, Davao City were invited as participants. Purposive sampling was utilized to select the study participants. Purposive sampling was a non-random sampling technique where researchers deliberately choose participants who possess specific characteristics or meet predetermined criteria relevant to the research objectives. Purposive sampling allowed researchers to target individuals most likely to provide rich and relevant information pertinent to the study objectives, thereby enhancing the depth and quality of the research findings.

2.3. Research Instrument—This study used two sets of instruments: one for the quanti-

tative phase and one for the qualitative phase. A panel of experts subjected these questionnaires to content validity testing and underwent pilot testing to test their validity and reliability. The experts' comments, corrections, and suggestions were incorporated into the final revisions of the questionnaires. The study used the researcher questionnaires to fit the respondents' context. The instrument is divided into three parts. The scaling was done by using one-half of the value of 5 as the average cut-off point or the fair level, with a uniform interval of 0.80. Quantitative Phase. In the quantitative phase, the researcher used an instrument

concerned with teachers' intellectual intuition. This questionnaire was indicated with Holistic-Big Picture, Holistic-Abstract, Inferential, and Affective. The scale's reliability obtained a Cronbach's alpha value of 0.943, which was described as excellent, indicating high reliability and consistency among the items. In answering the questionnaire, the respondents used the 5-Likert scale in which five or very extensive is the highest while one or not extensive was the lowest. As a guide in determining the extent of intellectual intuition, the researcher made use of the range of means, description, and interpretation as presented below:

Scale for Intellectual Intuition of Teachers

Range of Mean	Descriptive Level	Interpretation
4.20 – 5.00	Very Extensive	The intellectual intuition of teachers is always observed.
3.40 – 4.19	Extensive	The intellectual intuition of teachers is oftentimes observed.
2.60 – 3.39	Moderately Extensive	The intellectual intuition of teachers is sometimes observed.
1.80 – 2.59	Less Extensive	The intellectual intuition of teachers is rarely observed.
1.00 – 1.79	Not Extensive	The intellectual intuition of teachers is never observed.

Another tool used was about the instructional approach of teachers in technology-mediated classrooms. The researcher used a survey questionnaire with the following indicators: learning environment, digital learning, flipped classroom, and motivation and engagement, in the manner of answering the questionnaire. The reliability of the scale obtained a Cronbach's alpha value of 0.910, described as excellent, in-

dicating high reliability and consistency among the items. In answering the questionnaire, the respondents used the 5-Likert scale in which 5 or very extensive is the highest while 1 or not extensive is the lowest. As a guide in determining the extent of instructional approach of teachers in technology-mediated classroom, the researcher made use of the range of means, description and interpretation as presented below:

2.4. *Qualitative Phase*—In qualitative phase, the researcher conducted an IDI and FGD with the total of 10 elementary school teachers using a semi-structured interview. The researcher-made semi-structured interview guide was composed of general question with probing questions

Scale for Instructional Approach of Teachers in a Technology-Mediated Classroom

Range of Mean	Descriptive Level	Interpretation
4.20 – 5.00	Very Extensive	The instructional approach of teachers in a technology-mediated classroom is always manifested.
3.40 – 4.19	Extensive	The instructional approach of teachers in a technology-mediated classroom is often-times manifested.
2.60 – 3.39	Moderately Extensive	The instructional approach of teachers in a technology-mediated classroom is sometimes manifested.
1.80 – 2.59	Less Extensive	The instructional approach of teachers in a technology-mediated classroom is rarely manifested.
1.00 – 1.79	Not Extensive	The instructional approach of teachers in a technology-mediated classroom is never manifested.

to elaborate and dig deeper into the thoughts of the participants regarding the topic. This interview guide was developed upon consultation and reviewed by the experts and undergone several processes to accommodate their suggestions. The components to be validated include the language and the conceptual levels of questions if suited to the participants’ level of understanding, the suitability of the items to the research design in which there should be no leading questions, and the alignment of the interview questions to the objective of the study.

2.5. *Data Gathering Procedure*—The researcher took steps to conduct the study after the validation of the research questionnaire. The researcher secured the permission to conduct the study. The researcher secured the endorsement from the Dean of the Graduate School in The Rizal Memorial Colleges, Inc., Davao City; and the ethical clearance certificate from RMC-Research Ethics Committee (RMC-REC). The endorsement letter from the Dean of the Graduate School in Rizal Memorial Colleges, Inc., Davao City; and the ethical clearance certificate from RMC-Research Ethics Committee (RMC-REC) were attached to the permission letters to be endorsed to the school principals of the selected public schools in Buhangin District, Davao City. Before data collection, the researchers obtained informed consent from all participants, explaining the purpose of the study, the voluntary nature of participation, and the confidentiality of their responses. Respondents were allowed to ask questions and clarify any concerns before agreeing to take part in the study. The researcher explained that the survey questionnaires measure their perceptions of intellectual intuition domains and instructional approaches in a technology-mediated classroom. In the quantitative phase, survey questionnaires were distributed to Buhangin District, Davao City elementary school teachers. The data col-

lected through these questionnaires served as the basis for analyzing the variables. After the questionnaire was retrieved, each respondent's scores were tallied to organize the data per indicator. After that, each score was subjected to descriptive and inferential analysis using SPSS. In the qualitative phase, the researcher conducted in-depth interviews with elementary school teachers in Buhangin District, Davao City to gather rich and detailed information about their perception towards intellectual intuition domains and instructional approach in technology-mediated classroom. The interviews were conducted in a private and comfortable setting, such as the participant's homes or schools, to ensure confidentiality and encourage open communication. The researcher used open-ended questions and prompts to elicit detailed responses from the students, allowing them to share their thoughts, feelings, and experiences in their own words. During the interviews, the researcher took detailed notes and recorded audio or video with the participants' consent. This allowed for a comprehensive record of the interviews, capturing the nuances of the students' responses and providing rich data for analysis. Further, quantitative data were analyzed using statistical techniques such as descriptive statistics, correlation analysis, and inferential statistics to examine relationships between variables, differences between groups, and the overall distribution of responses. Furthermore, qualitative data were analyzed using thematic analysis or another appropriate qualitative method. Researchers identified recurring themes, patterns, and insights within the interview transcripts, focusing on how participants conceptualized and experienced intellectual intuition domains and instructional approach in technology-mediated classroom. Lastly, the researcher synthesized quantitative and qualitative findings, weaving together both data sets to develop a comprehensive narrative addressing the research objectives. They interpreted the findings in light of existing literature and theoretical frameworks, drawing meaningful conclusions about the topic.

2.6. Trustworthiness of the Study—To establish the study's trustworthiness, the researcher followed the four proposed criteria for evaluating interpretive research work by Lincoln and Guba (1985): credibility, transferability, dependability, and confirmability. This study's trustworthiness was addressed through a thorough data collection by survey and in-depth interview, supported by FGD for triangulation. **Credibility.** In the study about the influence of intellectual intuition domains on instructional approach in technology-mediated classrooms, credibility was established through several key strategies. Firstly, the researcher employed method triangulation by using both quantitative and qualitative data. This involved collecting quantitative data through surveys to identify general patterns and relationships, followed by qualitative data through in-depth interviews and classroom observations to explore these patterns further. By corroborating the findings across different methods, the researcher ensured a more accurate and credible representation of the teachers' experiences and perspectives. Additionally, member checking was utilized to enhance credibility. After the qualitative data were collected and analyzed, the researcher shared the findings with the participants to confirm the accuracy and authenticity of the interpretations. This process allowed participants to verify that their experiences were correctly understood and represented, thereby reducing researcher bias and ensuring that the findings genuinely reflected the teachers' perspectives. Prolonged engagement in the field also contributed to credibility, as the researcher spent ample time observing classrooms and interacting with participants to build trust and gain deeper insights into their instructional practices and intuitive decision-making processes. **Transferability.** To address transferability, the researcher provided detailed descriptions

of the research context, participants, and processes involved in the study. This thick description included comprehensive information about the school settings, the specific technologies used in the classrooms, and the demographic characteristics of the teachers involved. By offering a rich, detailed account of the study environment and the participants' backgrounds, the researcher enabled other educators and researchers to determine the extent to which the findings might apply to similar contexts. Moreover, the researcher ensured that the sampling strategy was purposive and included a diverse range of participants who varied in terms of teaching experience, subject areas, and familiarity with technology. This diversity allowed for a broader understanding of how intellectual intuition domains influence instructional approaches across different contexts within elementary education. By documenting these variations and the conditions under which the findings were observed, the researcher provided a foundation for assessing the potential transferability of the study's conclusions to other educational settings. Dependability. To establish dependability, the researcher maintained a detailed audit trail throughout the study, documenting each step of the research process. This included records of data collection methods, data analysis procedures, and the rationale for methodological choices. By providing a clear and transparent account of how the study was conducted, other researchers can follow and replicate the procedures, thereby enhancing the study's reliability. Additionally, the researcher conducted peer debriefing sessions with colleagues and experts in educational research. These sessions involved discussing the research design, data collection, and analysis methods, as well as the emerging findings. Peer debriefing helped to identify any inconsistencies or biases in the research process and provided an opportunity to refine the study's approach. By incorporating feedback from these discussions, the researcher ensured that the study's methods were sound and that the findings were dependable and accurately represented the influence of intellectual intuition on instructional approaches in technology-mediated classrooms. Confirmability. Confirmability was achieved through rigorous efforts to minimize researcher bias and ensure the objectivity of the study's findings. The researcher employed reflexivity by keeping a reflective journal throughout the study, documenting personal assumptions, biases, and reflections on the research process. This practice allowed the researcher to remain aware of potential influences on the data collection and analysis and to take steps to mitigate these biases. Moreover, the researcher used triangulation of data sources, including surveys, interviews, and classroom observations, to corroborate the findings. This approach ensured that the conclusions drawn were based on multiple perspectives and types of data, rather than relying on a single source. Additionally, the researcher provided detailed descriptions of the data analysis procedures, including coding schemes and thematic development, allowing others to trace the derivation of the findings. By maintaining transparency and systematically cross-checking data, the researcher upheld confirmability and ensured that the study's results were grounded in the participants' experiences rather than personal interpretations.

2.7. Data Analysis—Quantitative Phase The following were the statistical tools utilized by the researcher in processing the gathered data: Mean. This was useful in characterizing the intellectual intuition and instructional approach of teachers in technology-mediated classroom in Buhangin District, Davao City. *Pearson-r Analysis.* It was applied to evaluate the relationship between intellectual intuition and instructional approach of teachers in technology-mediated classroom in Buhangin District, Davao City. *Qualitative Phase* In the qualitative phase of the sequential explanatory mixed method design, the researcher employed

in-depth interviews and focus group discussions to delve deeper into the quantitative findings regarding the influence of intellectual intuition domains on the instructional approaches of teachers in technology-mediated classrooms. Initially, the researcher conducted in-depth interviews with a select group of teachers who exhibited significant patterns in the quantitative phase. These interviews aimed to explore the nuanced aspects of their intellectual intuition and how it guided their instructional decisions. The researcher used a semi-structured interview guide, allowing for flexibility in responses while ensuring that key themes were consistently addressed. This approach facilitated a comprehensive understanding of individual experiences and perspectives, capturing the essence of how intuition manifested in their teaching practices. Following the in-depth interviews, the researcher organized focus group discussions to gather a broader range of insights and foster dynamic interactions among teachers. These discussions included diverse groups of participants from different schools and backgrounds, providing a platform for sharing experiences and strategies related to technology-mediated instruction. The focus groups were structured to encourage open dialogue, enabling participants to reflect on and discuss the commonalities and differences in their intuitive approaches. This collective exploration helped to validate and enrich the individual interview findings, offering a holistic view of the instructional approaches influenced by intellectual intuition. Combining these qualitative methods ensured a robust and thorough examination of the research question, aligning with the sequential explanatory design by effectively linking qualitative insights to the initial quantitative results.

Sequence, Emphasis, and Mixing Procedures In the sequential explanatory mixed method design, the researcher implemented a clear and structured sequence for data collection and analysis. The process began with the quan-

titative phase, where surveys were administered to a large sample of elementary school teachers to gather data on their use of intellectual intuition in technology-mediated instruction. This quantitative data provided a broad overview of patterns and relationships, which were then analyzed using statistical methods. The results from this initial phase informed the subsequent qualitative phase, where a smaller, purposively selected group of teachers was interviewed to gain deeper insights. The qualitative data collection involved semi-structured interviews, allowing the researcher to explore the nuances and contextual factors that influenced the quantitative findings. The emphasis in this study was initially on the quantitative data to identify general trends and relationships across a larger population of teachers. This approach provided a robust foundation for understanding the overall influence of intellectual intuition on instructional approaches. Once significant patterns were identified, the emphasis shifted to qualitative data to explain and contextualize these patterns. The qualitative phase aimed to provide rich, detailed narratives that could illuminate the underlying reasons and mechanisms behind the observed quantitative trends. By placing initial emphasis on quantitative data and then delving into qualitative data, the researcher ensured a comprehensive understanding of the phenomenon. The mixing procedures in this study were carefully planned to integrate the quantitative and qualitative data effectively. After the quantitative data analysis, the researcher used the results to develop specific questions and topics for the qualitative interviews, ensuring that the qualitative phase directly addressed the key findings from the quantitative phase. During the qualitative data analysis, the researcher compared and contrasted the qualitative insights with the quantitative results, looking for corroboration, explanation, and expansion of the initial findings. This integration was achieved through a process known as connecting, where the two

data sets were explicitly linked during analysis.

3. Results and Discussion

This reflects the presentation, analysis, and interpretation of findings. Specifically, this chapter reveals both quantitative and qualitative data relevant to addressing the research questions formulated in Chapter 1. The tabulated quantitative findings are presented in Tables 1-3, while qualitative findings are presented in Tables 4-5.

3.1. Intellectual Intuition of Teachers—Results in Table 1 show the summary of teachers’ intellectual intuition. It shows that the overall mean of teachers’ intellectual intuition is 3.33, which is described as moderately extensive and interpreted as sometimes observed. More so, the intellectual intuition of teachers in terms of holistic-big picture acquired the highest mean score of 3.58, which is described as comprehensive and interpreted as oftentimes observed. In contrast, intellectual intuition of teachers in terms of inferential got the lowest mean score of 3.02, described as moderately extensive, and interpreted as sometimes followed by the teachers. In the context of moderate levels of teaching practice, intellectual intuition plays a critical role in enhancing instructional effectiveness and student engagement. Teachers with well-developed intellectual intuition can swiftly adapt their teaching methods to suit different learning styles and classroom dynamics, thereby maintaining a balanced and responsive instructional approach. This result is congruent with Thomas et al.’s (2015) view that pedagogical intuition helps teachers create flexible and structured lesson plans, allowing for adjustments based on real-time feedback from students. Technological intuition enables teachers to integrate digital tools to enhance learning without overwhelming students or deviating from the core instructional objectives.

Table 1. Intellectual Intuition of Teachers in Buhangin District, Davao City

Indicators	Mean	Descriptive Equivalent
Holistic-Big Picture	3.58	Extensive
Holistic-Abstract	3.47	Extensive
Inferential	3.02	Moderately Extensive
Affective	3.26	Moderately Extensive
Overall	3.33	Moderately Extensive

Meanwhile, the table further shows that teachers’ intellectual intuition in terms of holistic-big picture was assessed by the respondents as extensive with a category mean of 3.58, interpreted as oftentimes observed by the respondents. The mean rating of the different items, as shown in Appendix A, ranges from 3.15 to 4.22. On one hand, the item “Tending to focus on the details of the teaching-related tasks” (see Appendix A) has a mean rating of 3.15, described as moderately extensive and interpreted as sometimes observed by the respon-

dents. On the other hand, the item “Being a big picture person” (see Appendix A) reflects a mean of 4.22, which is described as very extensive and interpreted as always observed by the respondents. The result implies that teachers could grasp the holistic view of education, recognizing the interconnectedness of various elements in the teaching and learning process. Teachers with high levels of this intuition can perceive the more prominent educational goals and outcomes, integrating them into their daily practices. The result supports the findings of Zollo et al. (2017) that teachers can align their teaching strategies with the broader curriculum and educational goals, ensuring that their classroom activities contribute to the overarching learning objectives. This enables teachers to customize their instruction to meet students’ diverse needs and abilities while keeping the big picture of student growth in mind. Concerning teachers’ intellectual intuition in terms of holistic-abstract, it acquired an extensive rating with a category mean of 3.47, meaning that the respondents often observe this domain of teachers’ intellectual intuition. The mean rating of the different items, as shown in Appendix A, ranges from 3.04 to 4.11. The item “Thinking in terms of theories” (see Appendix A) reflects a mean rating of 2.23, which is described as less extensive and interpreted as an item seldom observed. Meanwhile, the item “Enjoying thinking in abstract terms” (see Appendix A) shows a rating of 4.11, described as extensive and interpreted as an item oftentimes observed by the teachers. The result means that teachers could understand abstract educational theories but may find it challenging to apply them in practical classroom settings consistently. This supports the findings of Káplár et al. (2017) that teachers with average levels of this intuition may benefit from professional development and mentorship to bridge the gap between theoretical knowledge and practical application. Such initiatives can enhance teachers’ intuitive capa-

bilities, enabling them to integrate new pedagogical and technological insights more effectively into their daily teaching practices. Further, the table indicates teachers’ intellectual intuition in terms of inferential acquired a category mean of 3.02, which is described as moderately extensive, which means that the teachers sometimes observe this domain of teachers’ intellectual intuition. The table further reveals that the mean rating of the items, as shown in Appendix A, ranges from 2.04 to 3.46. It is noteworthy that item “Feeling that my intuitions come to me when doing activities” (see Appendix A) has a mean rating of 2.04, described as less extensive, interpreted as item rarely observed, while, the item “Be able to give reasons when I have” (see Appendix A) has a mean rating of 3.46, described as extensive and interpreted as item oftentimes observed by the teachers. This implies that teachers can analyze information, make deductive or inductive reasoning, and recognize cause-and-effect relationships. It enables them to process and interpret data effectively, supporting informed decision-making in their teaching practice. The result supports the idea of Remmers et al. (2014) that teachers with average levels of inferential intuition can interpret data and information. Still, they may not excel in making complex or nuanced inferences. They can design lessons and instructional activities that align with available data and information, ensuring that teaching is somewhat evidence-based. Furthermore, teachers’ intellectual intuition in terms of affective acquired a category mean of 3.26 described as moderately extensive, which means that this domain teachers’ intellectual intuition is sometimes observed in Davao City. The table further reveals that the mean rating of the items, as shown in Appendix A, ranges from 2.35 to 4.18. It is noteworthy that item “Preferring to use hunches in completing science activities” (see Appendix A) has a mean rating of 2.35, described as less extensive, interpreted as item is rarely observed while item “Allowing

emotional reactions to guide me in doing my tasks” (see Appendix A) has a mean rating of 4.18, described as extensive and interpreted as item oftentimes observed by the teachers. The result means that teachers were able to show the ability to empathize with students, recognize their emotional states, and respond to their needs effectively. This supports the findings of Kandasamy et al. (2016) that teachers at this level can maintain open and effective communication with students, promoting a positive teacher-student relationship. They can address student conflicts and issues with empathy and help students develop better social and emotional skills.

3.2. *Instructional Approach of Teachers in Technology-Mediated Classroom*—The results in Table 2 summarize the instructional approach of teachers in technology-mediated classrooms in Buhangin District, Davao City. As shown in the table, teachers’ instructional approach in technology-mediated classrooms obtained an overall mean score of 3.25 with a descriptive rating of moderately extensive and interpreted as sometimes manifested. In the context of a moderate level of instructional approach, teach-

ers can effectively utilize technology to engage students. Still, the depth and innovation of their methods might be limited compared to those of more experienced peers. These teachers can incorporate technology into their lessons, but their use of digital tools may not fully exploit the potential for interactive and innovative teaching practices. The findings align with Means et al. (2013), suggesting that teachers with an average level of proficiency in instructional approaches for technology-mediated classrooms can involve students in technology-based activities. However, their methods may lack the creativity and interactivity seen in the approaches of teachers with advanced proficiency. For teachers employing a moderate instructional approach in technology-mediated classrooms, the key is integrating technology in a way that complements and improves their existing practices. The findings are consistent with Radhakrishnan’s (2018) assertion that the instructional approach in technology-mediated classrooms is significant because it balances innovation with practicality. Teachers with moderate proficiency use technology to enhance their teaching methods rather than completely change them.

Table 2. Instructional Approach of Teachers in Technology-Mediated Classroom in Buhangin District, Davao City

Indicators	Mean	Descriptive Equivalent
Learning Environment	3.47	Moderately Extensive
Digital Learning	3.22	Moderately Extensive
Flipped Classroom	3.13	Moderately Extensive
Motivation and Engagement	3.17	Moderately Extensive
Overall	3.25	Moderately Extensive

Meanwhile, Table 2 shows that the instructional approach of teachers in technology-mediated classroom in terms of learning environment was described by the teachers as exten-

sive with a category mean of 3.47, interpreted as oftentimes manifested. The mean rating of the different items, as shown in Appendix A, ranges from 2.72 to 4.27. The item “Assigning

fairly and impartially in class” (see Appendix A) shows a mean rating of 2.72, which is described as less extensive and interpreted as this item rarely observed by the teachers. Further, the item “Making students share ideas and opinions freely and openly in the class” (see Appendix A) has a mean rating of 4.13, described as extensive and interpreted as this item often-times manifested. In the context of a moderate instructional approach, teachers can integrate digital tools into their teaching practices effectively. They use technology to supplement traditional methods, providing a balanced learning experience that improves educational outcomes without overwhelming students with too much digital content. The findings align with Bower’s (2019) perspective that teachers with moderate proficiency can effectively utilize various digital tools and resources for teaching. However, their usage may not be as advanced or creative as highly proficient teachers. These teachers balance traditional and digital learning methods, enhancing educational outcomes by leveraging digital resources without completely replacing traditional approaches. Concerning the instructional approach of teachers in technology-mediated classrooms in terms of digital learning, Table 2 reflects a moderately extensive category mean of 3.22, which means that the teachers sometimes manifest it. Notably, the mean ratings of the different items, as shown in Appendix A, range from 2.25 to 3.78. The table further reveals that the item “Communicating with the students when there are announcements or information” (see Appendix A) has a mean rating of 2.85, which is described as less extensive and interpreted as an item rarely manifested by the teachers. Meanwhile, the item “Conducting virtual classes before giving an activity” (see Appendix A) has a mean rating of 3.78 described as extensive and interpreted as an instructional approach of teachers in technology-mediated classroom is oftentimes observed. Teachers with mod-

erate proficiency in using technology create interactive and collaborative learning environments. By adapting their instruction to meet individual student needs, they ensure that each student is engaged and motivated, benefiting from a personalized learning experience. This supports Henrie’s (2016) assertion that teachers with moderate proficiency use technology to promote active participation and interaction among students, fostering a sense of community and collaboration. These teachers employ technology to tailor instruction to individual learning needs, ensuring personalized learning experiences for each student. Moreover, the table indicates that the instructional approach of teachers in technology-mediated classroom in terms of flipped classroom has a category mean of 3.13 described as moderately extensive and interpreted that this domain of the instructional approach of teachers in technology-mediated classroom is sometimes manifested. Adding on, the mean ratings of the different items range from 2.10 to 3.89. Specifically, the item “Engaging students in different activities in a flipped classroom” has a mean rating of 2.10, which is described as less extensive and interpreted as an item rarely manifested by teachers. The item “Conducting more lectures that improve the students’ understanding of the topic” reflects a mean rating of 3.89, which is described as extensive and interpreted as an item that the teachers in Buhangin District, Davao City oftentimes manifest. The flipped classroom model exemplifies how technology can be used proficiently to improve educational outcomes. Teachers who adopt this approach demonstrate advanced skills in using digital tools, which significantly enhances student learning experiences and outcomes. The findings are consistent with Fructuoso et al.’s (2023) view that the flipped classroom approach is efficient as it maximizes the benefits of technology-mediated instruction. Teachers who use this approach show high proficiency in employing digital tools

to enhance learning outcomes. Lastly, the instructional approach of teachers in technology-mediated classrooms in terms of motivation and engagement, as shown in the table, reflects a moderately extensive category mean of 3.17, which means that the teachers sometimes manifest it. Notably, the mean ratings of the different items range from 2.36 to 3.78. The table further reveals that the item Communicating with the students when there are announcements or information has a mean rating of 2.85, described as moderately extensive, and interpreted as the item sometimes manifested by the teachers. Meanwhile, the item Conducting virtual classes before giving an activity has a mean rating of 3.78 described as extensive and interpreted as an instructional approach of teachers in technology-mediated classroom is oftentimes observed. Maintaining a balance between traditional and digital teaching methods is crucial for student motivation and engagement. Teachers who moderately integrate technology into their instruction provide diverse and interactive learning experiences, ensuring that students remain interested and actively involved in their learning process. According to Shen et al. (2016), balancing traditional and innovative methods is essential for fostering motivation and engagement. Teachers with moderate proficiency use technology to enhance their instructional practices without overloading students with digital content, offering varied and interactive learning experiences that keep students motivated and engaged.

3.3. Significant Relationship Between Intellectual Intuition and Instructional Approach of Teachers in Technology-Mediated Classroom in Buhangin District, Davao City—The results of the analysis of the relationship between intellectual intuition and instructional approach of teachers in technology-mediated classrooms in Buhangin District in Davao City are presented. Bivariate correlation analysis using

Pearson Product Moment Correlation was utilized to determine the relationship between the variables mentioned. Table 3 shows that intellectual intuition has a significant positive relationship with the instructional approach of teachers in technology-mediated classroom with a p-value of .000 that is less than .05 level of significance (two-tailed) ($r = .965$, $p < 0.05$). This means that as the extent of intellectual intuition changes, the importance of the instructional approach of teachers in technology-mediated classrooms also significantly changes. Moreover, the table also shows that the intellectual intuition in terms of holistic-big picture, holistic-abstract, inferential, and affective are significantly correlated with instructional approach of teachers in technology-mediated classroom as evident on the correlation coefficient values of 0.888, 0.875, 0.673, and 0.665. This leads to rejecting the null hypothesis of no significant relationship between intellectual intuition and instructional approach of teachers in technology-mediated classroom in Buhangin District, Davao City. Teachers' intellectual intuition plays a crucial role in effectively navigating technology-mediated instruction. By predicting how different digital tools will affect student engagement and learning, teachers can proactively design lessons that enhance the benefits of technology. This strategic planning ensures that technology integration is adequate and balanced, improving the educational experience while avoiding potential pitfalls. The findings align with Wu's (2020) idea that intellectual intuition enables teachers to anticipate potential challenges and opportunities related to technology-mediated instruction. With this intuitive insight, teachers can predict how various technological tools might influence student engagement and learning outcomes. This foresight allows them to design and execute instructional activities that optimize the advantages of technology while minimizing any drawbacks.

Table 3. Significant Relationship Between Intellectual Intuition and Instructional Approach of Teachers in Technology-Mediated Classroom in Buhangin District, Davao City

Intellectual Intuition	r-value	p-value	Interpretation	Decision
Holistic-Big Picture	0.888*	0.000	Significant	Reject H ₀
Holistic-Abstract	0.875*	0.000	Significant	Reject H ₀
Inferential	0.673*	0.000	Significant	Reject H ₀
Affective	0.665*	0.000	Significant	Reject H ₀
Overall Intellectual Intuition	0.964*	0.000	Significant	Reject H₀

*Significant at $p < 0.05$.

3.4. *Standpoints of the Participants on the Quantitative Results Regarding the Extents of Intellectual Intuition and Instructional Approach of Teachers in Technology-Mediated Classroom*—Table 4 presents the standpoints of the participants on the quantitative results regarding the extensive rating of intellectual intuition of teachers, and the moderately extensive rating of instructional approach of teachers in technology-mediated classroom. From the standpoints of the participants regarding the quantitative results regarding the comprehensive rating of intellectual intuition of teachers, four emerging codes were identified: Innovative pedagogy, holistic understanding, student-centered focus, and strategic planning.

3.4.1. *Innovative Pedagogy*—Innovative pedagogy is an instructional approach that emphasizes using creative and novel teaching methods, strategies, and resources to enhance the learning experience. The concept of innovative pedagogy is closely linked to the intellectual intuition of teachers, as teachers with high levels of intellectual intuition are often more inclined to explore and implement innovative teaching practices. Teachers with moderate intellectual intuition recognize the value of incorporating new teaching methods, which can sig-

nificantly enhance critical thinking skills. Moderately intuitive teachers use innovative pedagogical strategies to enhance classroom management. Organizing activities effectively creates a more structured and less chaotic learning environment, which benefits both teaching and learning. Innovative pedagogy involves using creative and modern teaching methods to enhance student learning. For teachers with moderate levels of intellectual intuition, innovative pedagogy means integrating new ideas and technologies in a balanced and practical way. According to Thomas et al. (2015), teachers with moderate intellectual intuition may not always be at the forefront of technological innovation. Still, they adopt new methods that align well with their teaching goals. They experiment with innovative techniques that are manageable and beneficial, such as incorporating multimedia resources or interactive digital platforms. These teachers balance tried-and-true traditional methods and creative practices, ensuring that introducing new tools and strategies enhances rather than overwhelms the learning process.

3.4.2. *Holistic Understanding*—Teachers with intellectual intuition often exhibit a holistic understanding of education, perceiving the interconnections among various elements in the

teaching and learning process. They can adapt their practices to create a well-rounded, inclusive, and future-oriented educational experience for their students, while also addressing the complexities and challenges of the education system. A holistic approach allows teachers with moderate intellectual intuition to cater to their students' diverse needs. Blending traditional and technological methods provides a more inclusive and practical learning experience. Holistic understanding refers to a comprehensive perspective on teaching that includes awareness of various educational dimensions and integrating both traditional and digital methods. The result supports Brock's (2015) assertion that teachers with moderate intellectual intuition employ a holistic approach by blending different teaching methods to create a well-rounded educational experience. They recognize the importance of not relying solely on technology but using it to complement and enhance traditional strategies. This approach helps them address the diverse needs of students, providing a more prosperous and more inclusive learning environment. Their moderate intuition allows them to see the broader picture, ensuring that technology is an effective tool within a larger pedagogical framework.

3.4.3. Student-Centered Focus—A student-centered focus in education places the learner at the center of the teaching and learning process. It emphasizes tailoring instruction to meet individual students' needs, interests, and learning styles. The concept of a student-centered focus is closely tied to the intellectual intuition of teachers, as teachers with high levels of intellectual intuition often excel in designing and implementing student-centered learning experiences. These teachers aim for a balanced educational approach incorporating traditional and digital tools. Their moderate intellectual intuition allows them to blend these methods effectively, providing a comprehensive learning experience that leverages the strengths

of both approaches to benefit their students. A student-centered focus places students' needs, interests, and learning styles at the core of the instructional process. Teachers with moderate intellectual intuition prioritize adapting their methods to support student engagement and success. According to Wilder (2016), for teachers with moderate intellectual intuition, a student-centered focus means carefully selecting and utilizing technology that enhances student learning without overshadowing the fundamental educational goals. These teachers may not use the most cutting-edge tools but choose those that effectively meet their students' needs. They maintain clear and straightforward technology integration to ensure that the focus remains on student learning outcomes. This approach ensures that technology is a means to an end—enhancing student understanding and participation.

3.4.4. Strategic Planning—The concept of strategic planning is closely linked to the intellectual intuition of teachers, as teachers with high levels of intellectual intuition often excel in developing and implementing strategic educational plans. Intellectual intuition guides teachers in curriculum development. They can intuitively structure the curriculum to ensure it aligns with strategic goals and long-term outcomes, providing students with a well-rounded education. Acknowledging their resource constraints, these teachers utilize strategic planning to allocate their limited tools and time efficiently. This careful management reflects their moderate intellectual intuition, allowing them to maximize the benefits of technology within their available means and ensure that resources are used where they are most needed. Strategic planning involves setting goals, assessing needs, and organizing resources effectively to achieve desired educational outcomes. Teachers with moderate intellectual intuition use strategic planning to optimize their use of technology. As noted by Eckhardt et al. (2018),

strategic planning is crucial for teachers with moderate intellectual intuition because it allows them to thoughtfully integrate technology into their teaching. They may not have extensive technical expertise, but they can determine the most effective tools and methods to use in their classrooms through careful planning. The participants' standpoints on the quantitative results regarding the moderately extensive rating of teachers' instructional approaches in technology-mediated classrooms identified three emerging codes: digital literacy and skills, adaptive learning, and technology ethics and responsibility.

3.4.5. Digital literacy and skills—Digital literacy and skills are integrated into the instructional approach of teachers in technology-mediated classrooms. This foundational knowledge equips students to thrive in the digital age, empowering them to use technology effectively for learning, communication, problem-solving, and future success. Teachers' digital skills can develop over time with regular practice and training. A moderate starting point doesn't limit their potential for improvement; ongoing development is key. As noted by Radhakrishnan et al. (2018) noted that achieving advanced proficiency with technology may be challenging due to various factors such as time constraints, lack of resources, or limited training opportunities. As a result, their instructional approach remains moderate. However, even with basic digital skills, these teachers can still deliver effective lessons by focusing on fundamental tools that facilitate learning. They use familiar technologies to create engaging and interactive lessons, ensuring that integrating digital tools is manageable and beneficial for students. This practical application of digital literacy ensures that the quality of education is maintained, even if the technological integration is not cutting-edge.

3.4.6. Adaptive Learning—Adaptive learning is vital in technology-mediated classrooms because it enhances the learning experience,

supports individual students, improves educational outcomes, and provides valuable data for teachers and academic institutions. It reflects a shift toward student-centered, data-driven, and more effective education, meeting the diverse needs of learners in the digital age. Adaptive learning provides insights into each student's strengths and weaknesses, enabling teachers to make timely adjustments. This flexibility is crucial for effectively addressing diverse learning needs. Adaptive learning technologies provide significant benefits in technology-mediated classrooms by allowing teachers to tailor their teaching methods to meet the unique needs of each student. Teachers with moderate tech skills can effectively use these tools to monitor student progress and adjust their strategies accordingly. According to Sheerah (2020), this personalized approach helps in identifying students' strengths and weaknesses, enabling teachers to provide targeted support where needed. Teachers ensure that all students are engaged and challenged appropriately by focusing on adaptive learning, promoting better learning outcomes. The moderate use of adaptive learning technologies reflects a balanced approach that leverages technology without overwhelming the instructional process.

3.4.7. Technology Ethics and Responsibility—Teaching technology ethics and responsibility is essential for creating responsible, ethical, and informed digital citizens. It prepares students for the complexities of the digital world, empowers them to make ethical choices, and contributes to their overall personal and professional development. It is a fundamental component of a comprehensive instructional approach in technology-mediated classrooms. Teachers emphasize responsibility in technology use and adopt a moderate approach to identify and address any issues quickly. This ensures that students use technology appropriately and responsibly. In technology-mediated classrooms, it is crucial to instill a sense of responsibility and

ethical behavior in students when using digital tools. Amanda (2017) proposed that teachers with a moderate approach prioritize educating students about the proper and safe use of technology. They focus on guiding students to understand the implications of their digital actions and the importance of maintaining privacy, security, and respectful online interactions. This em-

phasis on ethics ensures that students become proficient in using technology and develop a conscientious attitude towards its use. Teachers can closely monitor and manage students' technology use by adopting a moderate approach, promptly addressing issues and reinforcing ethical practices.

Table 4. Standpoints of the Participants on the Quantitative Results Regarding The Extents of Intellectual Intuition and Instructional Approach of Teachers in Technology-Mediated Classroom

Essential Theme	Codes
Confirmed Extensive Rating of Intellectual Intuition of Teachers	Innovative Pedagogy
	Holistic Understanding
	Student-Centered Focus
	Strategic Planning
Confirmed Moderately Extensive Rating of Instructional Approach of Teachers in Technology-Mediated Classroom	Digital Literacy and Skills
	Adaptive Learning
	Technology Ethics and Responsibility

3.5. *Standpoints of the Participants on the Significant Relationship Between Intellectual Intuition and Instructional Approach of Teachers in Technology-Mediated Classroom*—Table 5 presents the participants' standpoints on the quantitative results regarding the significant relationship between intellectual intuition and instructional approach of teachers in technology-mediated classrooms. Three emerging codes were identified: critical thinking, multimodal learning, and efficiency.

3.5.1. *Critical Thinking*—Critical thinking is a cornerstone in the relationship between intellectual intuition and the instructional approach of teachers in technology-mediated

classrooms. It promotes effective decision-making, problem-solving, and digital literacy, ultimately enhancing the quality of education and preparing students for the demands of the modern world. Teachers with developed intellectual intuition seamlessly incorporate critical thinking into their teaching methods, using technology as an enhancement tool. This integration helps students consistently think critically across various subjects and activities. In technology-mediated classrooms, teachers with intellectual intuition can leverage digital tools to foster critical thinking. These teachers can identify and utilize educational technologies encouraging students to engage in analytical and

evaluative tasks, such as interactive simulations, problem-solving apps, and online discussion forums. According to Bazalais and Doleck (2018), by integrating these tools into their lessons, they create a learning environment that conveys information and encourages students to question, explore, and construct new knowledge. This approach enhances students' cognitive abilities and prepares them for complex real-world challenges.

3.5.2. Multimodal Learning—Multimodal learning is essential in the relationship between intellectual intuition and instructional approach, which is fundamental to enhancing the quality of education in technology-mediated classrooms. It acknowledges the diversity of students, fosters engagement, supports retention, and promotes critical thinking, ultimately creating a more inclusive and effective learning environment. Multimodal learning fosters greater student interaction, as it incorporates various engagement methods. Teachers with intellectual intuition are adept at selecting the right technological tools to facilitate these interactions, enhancing the overall learning experience. In a technology-mediated classroom, multimodal learning is essential for addressing the diverse needs of students. This supports the findings of Dai and Wang (2024) that teachers with intel-

lectual intuition can seamlessly integrate audio, video, interactive simulations, and hands-on activities to provide a rich and varied learning experience.

3.5.3. Efficiency—Efficiency is paramount in the relationship between intellectual intuition and the instructional approach of teachers in technology-mediated classrooms. It results in optimized resource utilization, adaptability to change, streamlined instruction, and improved learning outcomes, ultimately enhancing the quality of education and the overall learning experience for students. When teachers maximize the use of technology, lesson delivery becomes more efficient. This allows them to allocate more time to critical aspects of teaching, such as individualized instruction and student support, ultimately enhancing the learning experience. Efficient teaching practices are crucial in technology-mediated classrooms, with high potential for distraction and complexity. This supports the idea of Pandita and Kiran (2023) that Teachers with intellectual intuition can identify the most effective technological tools and strategies to enhance their instructional efficiency. This includes using digital platforms to automate routine tasks, such as grading and attendance, allowing more time for interactive and personalized instruction.

Table 5. Standpoints of the Participants on the Significant Relationship Between Intellectual Intuition and Instructional Approach of Teachers in Technology-Mediated Classroom

Essential Theme	Codes
Confirmed Significant Relationship Between Intellectual Intuition and Instructional Approach of Teachers in Technology-Mediated Classroom	Critical Thinking
	Multimodal Learning
	Efficiency

4. Conclusions and Recommendations

This part of the paper presents the researcher's conclusion and recommendation. The literature supports the discussion in the first chapters, and the conclusion consists of statements about the problem presented in this study.

4.1. Findings—This study aimed to determine the influence of intellectual intuition on the instructional approach of teachers in technology-mediated classroom in Buhangin District, Davao City using mixed methods specifically the sequential-explanatory design wherein adapted survey questionnaires will be used in the quantitative phase and through in-depth interview (IDI) and focus group discussion (FGD) in the qualitative phase. On one hand, in the quantitative phase of the study, adapted survey questionnaires were used to gather data from the teachers to determine the extent of intellectual intuition and the instructional approach of teachers in technology-mediated classroom. For the quantitative strand, the researcher used modified and enhanced adapted survey questionnaires, which were pilot tested in a nearby school to ensure high reliability and internal consistency of the items in the instrument. In contrast, a semi-structured interview guide was used in the qualitative strand. Based on the results, the summary of the findings was the following: Intellectual intuition of teachers in Buhangin District in Davao City got an overall mean of 3.42 with extensive descriptive rating. Also, intellectual intuition of teachers in terms of holistic-big picture, holistic-abstract, inferential, and affective obtained the mean scores of 3.58, 3.47, 3.02, and 3.26, respectively. The instructional approach of teachers in technology-mediated classrooms in Buhangin District in Davao City has an overall mean of 3.25 and a moderately extensive descriptive rating. Also, the instructional approach of teachers in technology-mediated classrooms in terms of learning environment, digital learning, flipped classroom, motivation, and engage-

ment obtained mean scores of 3.47, 3.22, 3.13, and 3.17, respectively. Intellectual intuition has a significant positive relationship with the instructional approach of teachers in technology-mediated classroom in Buhangin District in Davao City with a p-value of .000 that is less than .05 level of significance (two-tailed) ($r = .964$, $p < 0.05$). This means that as the intellectual intuition changes, the instructional approach of teachers in technology-mediated classrooms also changes significantly. From the standpoints of the participants regarding the quantitative results regarding the extensive rating of intellectual intuition, the four emerging codes are as follows: innovative pedagogy, holistic understanding, student-centered focus, and strategic planning. From the standpoints of the participants regarding the quantitative results regarding the moderately extensive rating of instructional approaches of teachers in technology-mediated classrooms, the three emerging codes are as follows: digital literacy and skills; adaptive learning; and technology ethics and responsibility. The participants' standpoints on the quantitative results regarding the significant relationship between intellectual intuition and instructional approach of teachers in technology-mediated classrooms are that critical thinking, multimodal learning, and efficiency are the three emerging codes.

4.2. Conclusions—Based on the findings of this study and within the limitations and restrictions (such as survey questionnaire and number of respondents), several conclusions are generated: Intellectual intuition of the teachers in Buhangin District, Davao City was extensive. Meanwhile, intellectual intuition of teachers in terms of holistic-big picture and

holistic-abstract obtained extensive descriptive ratings, while, intellectual intuition of teachers in terms of inferential and affective acquired moderately extensive ratings. The result denotes the deep understanding and insight experienced educators possess, allowing them to make rapid, accurate, and informed decisions in their teaching practice, which is often observed among teachers. The instructional approach of teachers in technology-mediated classroom in Buhangin District in Davao City was rated as moderately extensive. The instructional approach of teachers in technology-mediated classrooms regarding learning environment, digital learning, flipped classroom, motivation, and engagement has a moderately extensive rating. It implies that educators' methods, strategies, and practices when integrating technology into their teaching are sometimes manifested. Intellectual intuition significantly correlates positively with teachers' instructional approaches in technology-mediated classrooms. This implies that intellectual intuition can empower teachers to create a dynamic and practical instructional approach in technology-mediated classrooms. It enables them to adapt to changing technology, innovate their teaching practices, and prioritize a holistic understanding of education. The quantitative results on teachers' extensive intellectual intuition were further substantiated by codes (innovative pedagogy, holistic understanding, student-centered focus, and strategic planning) that emerged during the thematic analysis of the qualitative data, generally confirming the results of the quantitative aspects of the study. The quantitative results on the moderately extensive instructional approach of teachers in technology-mediated were further substantiated by codes (digital literacy and skills; adaptive learning; and technology ethics and responsibility) that emerged during the thematic analysis of the qualitative data, generally confirming the results of the quantitative aspects of the study. The quantitative results on the significant rela-

tionship between intellectual intuition and instructional approach of teachers in technology-mediated settings were further substantiated by codes (critical thinking, multimodal learning, and efficiency) that emerged during the thematic analysis of the qualitative data, generally confirming the results of the quantitative aspects of the study. The salient quantitative and qualitative findings revealed a parallel result. The corroborated finding means that the quantitative and qualitative findings merged and connected.

4.3. Recommendations—The Department of Education should provide sufficient funding and resources to support professional development programs that enhance teachers' digital literacy and instructional skills. They should also establish guidelines that encourage technology integration in a balanced and effective manner, ensuring it complements traditional teaching methods. To motivate teachers to improve their proficiency, incentives for continuous learning and certification in educational technology should be offered. Also, the Department of Education should invest in robust digital infrastructure to ensure all schools have access to reliable and up-to-date technological tools. School heads should prioritize ongoing professional development for teachers, focusing on digital literacy and effective instructional strategies for technology-mediated classrooms. They should foster a collaborative environment where teachers can share best practices and support each other in integrating technology. School heads can guide teachers in aligning their instructional approaches with the school's goals by implementing a clear vision for technology use in education. Additionally, they should ensure that technological resources are distributed equitably and used to support diverse learning needs. Teachers should actively seek out professional development opportunities to enhance their digital literacy and integrate technology effectively into their instructional approaches. They should use technology to create

engaging, interactive, and personalized learning experiences catering to their students' diverse needs. Collaborating with colleagues to share strategies and tools can help them refine their approach and stay updated with new technologies. Teachers should also regularly assess the impact of technology on student learning outcomes and adjust their methods accordingly. Students should be encouraged to embrace technology as a tool for learning, developing their digital literacy alongside traditional academic skills. They should be given opportunities to engage in activities that foster critical thinking, problem-solving, and collaboration using digital tools. Students should also be made aware of the ethical and responsible use of technology, ensuring they understand the importance of digital citizenship. Students' feedback regarding technology use in the classroom should be actively sought and considered to improve instructional practices. Future researchers should explore the long-term effects of moderate levels of intellectual intuition on student outcomes in technology-mediated classrooms. They should investigate how different professional development programs impact teachers' ability to integrate technology effectively. Comparative studies between schools with varying levels of technological integration can provide insights into best practices and potential areas for improvement. Additionally, research should focus on identifying the specific aspects of digital literacy and instructional strategies that significantly enhance student engagement and learning outcomes.

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